

Characterization of $PSU(3, q)$ by its order and one special conjugacy class size

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 19 April 2024</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Soleyman Askary</p>	<p>Suppose that G be a finite group, and let $N(G)$ be the set of conjugacy class sizes of G. By Thompson’s conjecture, if H is a finite non abelian simple group, G is a finite group with a trivial center, and $N(G) = N(H)$, then H and G are isomorphic. Chen et al. contributed interestingly to Thompsons conjecture under a weak condition. In this article, we investigate validity of Thompsons conjecture under a weak condition for the projective special unitary groups. This work implies that Thompsons conjecture holds for the $PSU(3, q)$, where q is prime power.</p> <p>2020 Mathematics Subject Classification: 20D08, 20D60.</p>
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INTRODUCTION

All groups considered in this paper are finite, and simple groups are non abelian. For convenience, we use g^G and $|g^G|$ to denote the conjugacy class of G containing g and the size of g^G , respectively. Denote by $N(G) = \{|g^G| : g \in G\}$. Suppose that $\pi(G)$ denote the set of primes dividing the order of G . For a group G , we construct the prime graph of G which is denoted by $\Gamma(G)$ as follows: the vertex set is $\pi(G)$ and two distinct primes p and q are joined by an edge if and only if G contains an element of order pq . Let $t(G)$ be the number of connected components of $\Gamma(G)$ and let $\pi_1, \pi_2, \dots, \pi_{t(G)}$ be the connected components of $\Gamma(G)$. If $2 \in \pi(G)$, then we always suppose that $2 \in \pi_1(G)$. $|G|$ can be expressed as a product of co-prime positive integers $OC_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, t(G)$, where $\pi(OC_i) = \pi_i$. These OC_i ’s are called the order components of G and the set of order components of G will be denoted by $OC(G)$. Also we call $OC_2, \dots, OC_{t(G)}$ the odd order

components of G . Let n be a positive integer and p be a prime number. Then $|n|_p$ denotes the p -part of n .

In 1987, John Thompson posted the following conjecture concerning $N(G)$.

Thompson’s conjecture (See [16], Question 12.38).

Let G be a group with trivial central. If H is a simple group satisfying $N(G) = N(H)$, then $G \cong H$. In [8], [9], Thompson’s conjecture is verified for a few finite simple groups. In [11], Chen contributed to Thompson’s conjecture under a week condition. The only used order and one or two special conjugacy class sizes of simple groups and characterized successfully sporadic simple groups, A_{10} , $PSL(4, 4)$, $PSL(2, p)$, $PSL(n, 2)$, ${}^2D_n(2)$, ${}^2D_{n+1}(2)$, $C_n(2)$, alternating group of degree p , $p + 1$, $p + 2$ and symmetric group of degree p , where p is prime number.

In this paper, we are going to characterize the projective special unitary group $PSU(3, q)$ by its order and one special conjugacy class length, where $q > 5$ is a prime power.

According to the classification theorem of finite simple groups and [12], [15], [19], we can list the order components of finite simple groups with disconnected prime graphs as in Tables 1-4 in [9]. All further

unexplained notation is standard and we refer to [12], for example.

1. First section

Definition 1. A Frobenius group is a transitive permutation group in which the stabilizer of any two points is trivial.

Definition 2. A group G is a 2-Frobenius group if there exists a normal series $1 \trianglelefteq H \trianglelefteq K \trianglelefteq G$ such that K and G/H are Frobenius groups with kernels H and K/H , respectively.

Lemma 1. [7] Let G be a Frobenius group of even order with kernel K and complement H . Then $t(G) = 2$, the prime graph components of G are $\pi(H)$ and $\pi(K)$ and the following assertions hold:

- (1) K is nilpotent;
- (2) $|K| \equiv 1 \pmod{|H|}$.

Lemma 2. [7] Let G be a 2-Frobenius group, i.e., G is a finite group and has a normal series $1 \trianglelefteq H \trianglelefteq K \trianglelefteq G$ such that K and G/H are Frobenius groups with kernels H and K/H , respectively. Then:

- (a) $t(G) = 2$, $\pi_1 = \pi(G/K) \cup \pi(H)$ and $\pi_2 = \pi(K/H)$;
- (b) G/K and K/H are cyclic, $|G/K| \equiv |K/H| - 1$ and $G/K \leq \text{Aut}(K/H)$.

Lemma 3. [19] If G is a finite group such that $t(G) \geq 2$, then G has one of the following structures:

- (a) G is a Frobenius group or 2-Frobenius group;
- G has a normal series $1 \trianglelefteq H \trianglelefteq K \trianglelefteq G$ such that $\pi(H) \cup \pi(G/K) \subseteq \pi_1$ and K/H is a nonabelian simple group. In particular, H is nilpotent, $G/K \cong \text{Out}(K/H)$ and the odd order components of G are the odd order components of K/H .

Lemma 4. [17] If $n \geq 6$ is a natural number, then there are at least $s(n)$

- prime numbers p_i such that $(n + 1)/2 < p_i < n$. Here
- $s(n) = 1$, for $6 \leq n \leq 13$;
- $s(n) = 2$, for $14 \leq n \leq 17$;
- $s(n) = 3$, for $18 \leq n \leq 37$;
- $s(n) = 4$, for $38 \leq n \leq 41$;
- $s(n) = 5$, for $42 \leq n \leq 47$;
- $s(n) = 6$, for $n \geq 48$.

Lemma 5. [14] Let $M = PSU(3, q)$, where $q > 5$ and $OC_2 = \frac{q^2 - q + 1}{d}$ with $d = (3, q + 1)$.

- (i) If $p \in \pi_1(M)$ and $p^\alpha \mid |M|$, then $p^{\alpha-1}$ not congruent to 0 modulo OC_2 .
- (ii) If $p \in \pi_1(M)$, $p^\alpha \mid |M|$, then $p^{\alpha+1} \equiv 0 \pmod{OC_2}$ if and only if $p^\alpha = q^3$ or $q = 7$ and $p^\alpha = 2^7$, for every positive integer α .
- (iii) If $d = 3$ and $(OC_2 - 1) \mid |M|$, then $q = 8$.

2. Second section

Main Theorem Let G be a group and $q = p^\alpha$ is prime power. Then $G \cong PSU(3, q)$ if and only if $|G| = |PSU(3, q)|$ and G has one conjugacy class size $|PSU(3, q)|/r$, where $r = \frac{q^2 - q + 1}{(3, q + 1)}$ be a prime number.

Proof. By [13], $PSU(3, q)$ has one conjugacy class size $|GU(3, q)|/q^3 + 1$. Since the necessity of the theorem is easy, we only need to prove the sufficiency.

By hypothesis, there exists an element g of order r in G such that

$C_G(g) = \langle g \rangle$ and $C_G(g)$ is a Sylow r -subgroup of G . By The Sylow theorem, we have that $C_G(h) = \langle h \rangle$ for any element h in G of order r . So, $\{r\}$ is a prime graph component of G and $t(G) \geq 2$. Therefore, r is the maximal prime divisor of $|G|$ and an odd order component of G .

Now, if $t(G) = 2$, then $OC(G) = OC(PSU(3, q))$. By [14],

$$G \cong PSU(3, q).$$

If $t(G) \geq 3$, then we will show that there is no such group. Since $t(G) \geq 3$, Lemma 1, and 2 show that G is neither a Frobenius group nor a 2-Frobenius group. By Lemma 3, G has normal series $1 \trianglelefteq H \trianglelefteq K \trianglelefteq G$ such that K/H is a nonabelian simple group and r is an odd order component of K/H . Moreover, $t(K/H) \geq 3$.

According to the classification theorem of finite simple groups and the results in Tables 1-4 in [9], K/H is an alternating group, sporadic group or simple group of Lie type, which consider in the following.

Step 1. K/H is not an sporadic simple group.

Proof. Suppose that K/H is an sporadic simple group. Since $q > 5$, $r \geq 19$ and hence $r \in \{19, 23, 29, 31, 37, 41, 43, 47, 59, 67, 71\}$.

Now, if $r = 19$ and $d = 3$, then $q = 8$, $|PSU(3, 8)| = 2^9 \cdot 3^4 \cdot 7 \cdot 19$ and $K/H \in \{J_1, J_3, On, TH, BN\}$, so $5 \mid |K/H|$, which is a contradiction. If $d = 1$, then $q(q - 1) = 18$, which is impossible. By the same method, we can consider the other possibilities for r .

Step 2. K/H can not be an alternating group A_m , where $m \geq 5$.

Proof. If $K/H = A_m$, then since $r \in \pi(K/H)$, $m \geq r$. Also, since $q > 5$ is a prime power, $r \geq 19$. Thus by Lemma 4, there exists a prime number $s \in \pi(A_m)$ such that $(r + 1)/2 < s < r$. Also, since $|K/H| \mid |G|, s \mid r \cdot q^3(q + 1)^2(q - 1)$, which is impossible.

Step 3. K/H is not a simple group of Lie type.

Proof. Assume that K/H is isomorphic to one of the finite simple groups:

Case 1. Let $t(K/H) = 3$. Then $r \in \{OC_2(K/H), OC_3(K/H)\}$:

1.1. If $K/H \cong A_1(q')$, where $4 \mid q'$, then the odd order components of K/H are $q' + 1$ and $q' - 1$. If $q' + 1 = r$, then $q' = r - 1 = \frac{q^2 - q + 1}{d} - 1$ and hence, either $q' = q(q - 1)$ or $q' = \frac{(q + 1)(q - 2)}{3}$, which are impossible. If $q' - 1 = r$, then by Lemma 5, we get a contradiction.

1.2. If $K/H \cong A_1(q')$, where $4 \mid q' + 1$, then $q' = r$ or $\frac{q' - 1}{2} = r$. Now, if $\frac{q' - 1}{2} = r$, then $q' - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{r}$, which is a contradiction by Lemma 5 (i). If $q' = r$ and $d = 1$, then $q' = q^2 - q + 1$ and hence,

$$|K/H| = q(q^2 - q + 1)(q^2 - q + 2)(q - 1) / 2.$$

Since $|K/H| \mid |G|$ and $\frac{q^2 - q + 2}{2}$ not divides $|G|$, we get a contradiction. If $d = 3$, then $(r - 1) \parallel |G|$ and hence, by Lemma 5(iii), we must have $q = 8$ and $r = 19$. Hence $q' = 19$. But $5 \mid |\text{PSL}(2, 19)|$ and 5 not divides $|\text{PSU}(3, 8)|$, which is a contradiction.

1.3. If $K/H \cong A_1(q')$, where $4 \mid q' - 1$, then $q' = r$ or $\frac{q' + 1}{2} = r$. Since the possibility $q' = r$ is discussed in former case, we suppose that $\frac{q' + 1}{2} = r$. Then $q' + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{r}$, By Lemma 5(ii), we can conclude that $q = 7$ or $q' = q^3$. Now, if $q = 7$, then $q' = 2^7$. Since 4 not divides $2^7 - 1$, we get a contradiction. If $q' = q^3$, then $|K/H| = |\text{PSL}(2, q')| = q^3(q^3 - 1)(q^3 + 1) / 2$.

On the other hand, $|K/H| \mid |G|$, thus $q^2 + q + 1$ must be divide $(q + 1)^2$, which is a contradiction.

1.4. If $K/H \cong G_2(q')$ where $q' = 3^{2t+1} > 3$, then $q' - \sqrt{3q'} + 1 = \frac{q^2 - q + 1}{d}$ or $q' + \sqrt{3q'} + 1 = \frac{q^2 - q + 1}{d}$. Let $(3, q) = 1$. Assume that $q' - \sqrt{3q'} + 1 = \frac{q^2 - q + 1}{d}$ and $d = 1$, thus $3^{t+1}(3^t + 1) = q(q - 1)$. Now, since $(3, q) = 1$, 3 does not divide q and hence $|q - 1|_3 = 3^{t+1}$.

Thus $|G|_3 = |q - 1|_3 = 3^{t+1}$. On the other hand, $3^{3(2t+1)} = |K/H|_3 \leq |G|_3 = 3^{t+1}$, which is a contradiction.

If $d = 3$, then $q' + \sqrt{3q'} + 1 = \frac{q^2 - q + 1}{3}$ and hence, $3^{t+2}(3^t + 1) = (q + 1)(q - 2)$. Thus either $3^{t+1} \mid (q + 1)$ and $(q - 2) \mid 3(3^t + 1)$ or $3^{t+1} \mid (q - 2)$ and $(q + 1) \mid 3(3^t + 1)$. This forces $(q + 1) = 3^{t+1}$ and $(q - 2) = 3(3^t + 1)$. This guarantees that $|G|_3 = 3^{2t+2}$. Also, $3^{3(2t+1)} = |K/H|_3 \leq |G|_3 = 3^{2t+2}$, which is a contradiction. If $q' - \sqrt{3q'} + 1 = \frac{q^2 - q + 1}{d}$, then similar to the above we get a contradiction. Assume that $(3, q) \neq 1$. So $d = 1$ and $q' \pm \sqrt{3q'} + 1 = q^2 + q + 1$, this forces $q = 3^{t+1}$ and $q - 1 = 3^t \pm 1$, which is a contradiction.

1.5. If $K/H \cong D_s(3)$, where $s = 2^t + 1 \geq 5$, then

$$\frac{3^s + 1}{4} = \frac{q^2 - q + 1}{d} \text{ or } \frac{3^{s-1} + 1}{2} = \frac{q^2 - q + 1}{d}. \text{ If } \frac{3^s + 1}{4} = r, \text{ then}$$

$$3^{s(s-1)}(3^{s-1} - 1)(3^{s-1} + 1) \prod_{i=1}^{s-2} (3^{2i} - 1) \mid q^3(q + 1)^2(q - 1)$$

On the other hand, $r^6 = \frac{(3^s + 1)^6}{4096} \leq 3^{6s}$ and

$$3^{2s(s-1)-s} < 3^{s(s-1)}(3^{s-1} - 1)(3^{s-1} + 1) \prod_{i=1}^{s-2} (3^{2i} - 1) \mid q^3(q + 1)^2(q - 1)$$

, which implies that $2s(s - 1) < 7s$ and hence, $s < 5$,

which is a contradiction. If $\frac{3^{s-1} + 1}{2} = \frac{q^2 - q + 1}{d}$, then similar to the above, we get a contradiction.

1.6. If $K/H \cong D_{s+1}(2)$, where $s = 2^n - 1$ and $n \geq 2$,

$$\text{then } 2^s + 1 = \frac{q^2 - q + 1}{d} \text{ or } 2^{s+1} + 1 = \frac{q^2 - q + 1}{d}. \text{ If}$$

$$2^s + 1 = r, \text{ then } 2^s = q(q - 1) \text{ or } 2^s = \frac{(q + 1)(q - 2)}{3},$$

which is impossible. The same reasoning rules out the case when $2^{s+1} + 1 = r$.

1.7. If $K/H \cong F_4(q')$, where q' is even, then

$$q'^4 + 1 = \frac{q'^2 - q' + 1}{d} \text{ or } q'^4 - q'^2 + 1 = \frac{q'^2 - q' + 1}{d}.$$

If $q'^4 + 1 = r$, then $q'^{24}(q'^6 - 1)^2(q'^4 - 1)^2(q'^4 - q'^2 + 1) \mid q'^3(q' + 1)^2(q' - 1)$. Also, $r^6 = (q'^4 + 1)^6 < (q'^5)^6 = q'^{30}$ and $q'^{24}(q'^6 - 1)^2(q'^4 - 1)^2(q'^4 - q'^2 + 1) \leq q'^3(q' + 1)^2(q' - 1) < r^6 < q'^{30}$, which is a contradiction. If $q'^4 - q'^2 + 1 = r$, then similar to the above, we get a contradiction. By the same method, we can prove that K/H cannot be a simple group $F_4(q')$, where q' is odd.

1.8. If $K/H \cong E_7(2)$, then $r \in \{73, 127\}$. Therefore, $r = 73$ and $q = 9$.

So $|PSU(3, 9)| = 2^{10} \cdot 3^9 \cdot 5^2 \cdot 73$. On the other hand, $13 \mid |E_7(2)|$, which is a contradiction. By the same method, we can prove that K/H cannot be a simple group $E_7(3)$.

1.9. If $K/H \cong A_2(2), A_2(4)$ or ${}^2A_5(2)$, then since $q > 5$ is a prime power, we get a contradiction.

1.10. If $K/H \cong {}^2F_4(q')$, where $q' = 2^{2t+1} \geq 2$, then

$$r = q'^2 \pm 2q'^3 +$$

$q' \pm 2q' + 1$. In both cases, we can see at once that $|K/H| > |G|$, which is a contradiction.

Case 2. Let $t(K/H) \in \{4, 5\}$. Then

$$r \in \{OC_2(K/H), OC_3(K/H), OC_4(K/H), OC_5(K/H)\},$$

as follows:

2.1. If $K/H \cong {}^2B_2(q')$, where $q' = 2^{2t+1}$ and $t \geq 1$, then

$$r \in \{q' - 1, q' \pm \sqrt{2q'} + 1\}. \text{ If } q' - 1 = r, \text{ then by Lemma}$$

5(i), we get a contradiction. Assume that $q' - \sqrt{2q'} + 1 = r$

. Then $q'^2 - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{r}$. Therefore, $q'^2 = 2^7$ or $q'^2 = q'^3$. Now, since 2^7 is not a square, we get a

contradiction. If $q'^2 = q'^3$, then q' is even. Let $d = 1$.

Thus $2^{2t+1} - 2^{t+1} = q'(q - 1)$ and since $(q, q - 1) = 1$, we conclude that $q = 2^{t+1}$ and $r < q^9$, which is a

contradiction. . If $d = 3$ and we assume that $q = 2^m$, then $2(3 \cdot 2^{2t} - 3 \cdot 2^t + 1) = 2^m(2^m - 1)$, which implies that $m = 1$. But $q > 5$ and hence, we get a contradiction. For

$q' + 2q' + 1 = r$, similar to the above we get a contradiction.

2.2. If $K/H \cong A_2(4)$, then $\frac{q^2 - q + 1}{d} \in \{5, 7, 9\}$. Since $q > 5$ is a prime power, we get a contradiction.

2.3. If $K/H \cong {}^2E_6(2)$, then $\frac{q^2 - q + 1}{d} \in \{13, 17, 19\}$.

Let $\frac{q^2 - q + 1}{d} = 19$ and $d = 3$, then $q(q - 1) = 56$, $q =$

8 and $|PSU(3, 8)| = 2^9 \cdot 3^4 \cdot 7 \cdot 19$. On the other hand $13 \mid |{}^2E_6(2)|$, which is a contradiction. For $r \in \{13, 17\}$, similar to the above we get a contradiction.

2.4. If $K/H \cong E_8(q')$, then

$$r \in \{q'^8 - q'^7 + q'^5 - q'^4 + q'^3 - q' + 1, q'^8 + q'^7 - q'^5 - q'^4 - q'^3 + q'^8 - q'^6 + q'^4 - q'^2 + 1, q'^8 - q'^4 + 1\}.$$

If $q'^8 - q'^7 + q'^5 - q'^4 + q'^3 - q' + 1 = r$, then $r < q'^9$. On

the other hand, $r^6 < q'^{54}$ and $|G| < r^6$. Since $q'^{120} \mid |K/H|$ and $|K/H| \mid |G|$, we get a contradiction. For other cases, similarly we get a contradiction.

3. Third section

Corollary 1. Let $q = p^\alpha$ be a prime power. Then Thompson's conjecture holds for the simple groups

$$PSU(3, q), \text{ where } \frac{q^2 - q + 1}{(3, q + 1)} \text{ is prime number.}$$

Proof. Let G be a group with trivial center and $N(G) = N(PSU(3, q))$. Then it is proved in [6], that $|G| = |PSU(3, q)|$. Hence, the corollary follows from the main theorem.

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